

5. Characters 353 and 354 from the original list were split into four distinct characters (353, 354, 381, and 382), but the scores for the original characters remained unchanged. The scores for the newly added characters 381 and 382 are listed below:

Marasuchus lilloensis -?

Silesaurus opolensis -?

Eoraptor lunensis -?

Herrerasaurus ischiugualastensis -?

Abrictosaurus consors ?0

Fruitadens haagarorum 12

Tianyulong confuciusi ??

Heterodontosaurus tucki 12

Pisanosaurus mertii ??

Pegomastax africanus ??

Echinodon becklesii ??

Manidens condorensis ??

Eocursor parvus 11

Lesothosaurus diagnosticus 0-

Agilisaurus louderbacki ?0

Yandusaurus hongheensis ??

Haya griva 12

Hexinlusaurus multidens 1?

Changchunsaurus parvus 1?

Hypsilophodon foxii 12

Jeholosaurus shangyuanensis 12

Orodromeus makelai 12

Yueosaurus tiantaiensis ??

Gideonmantellia amosanjuanae 10

Koreanosaurus boseongensis 12

Parksosaurus warreni ??

Zephyrosaurus schaffi ??

Thescelosaurus neglectus ?0

Gasparinisaura cincosaltensis 12

Dryosaurus altus 10

Zalmoxes robustus 10

Tenontosaurus tilletti 12

Mantellisaurus atherfieldensis ??

Probactrosaurus gobiensis 1?

Ouranosaurus nigeriensis 12

Camptosaurus dispar 00

Stenopelix valdensis ??

Yinlong downsi 1?

Hualianceratops wucaiwansensis ??

Chaoyangsaurus youngi ??

Xuanhuaceratops niei ??

Liaoceratops yanzigouensis ??
Aquilops americanus ??
Yamaceratops dorngobiensis ??
Archaeoceratops oshimai ??
Auroraceratops rugosus 12
Koreaceratops hwaseongensis ??
Albalophosaurus yamaguchiorum ??
Protoceratops andrewsi ??
Bagaceratops rozhdestvenskyi ??
Leptoceratops gracilis ??
Psittacosaurus mongoliensis ??
Psittacosaurus lujiatunensis ??
Mosaiceratops azumai ??
Scelidosaurus harrisonii 11
Scutellosaurus lawleri 0-
Emausaurus ernsti ??
Minmi paravertebra ??
Gargoyleosaurus parkpinorum ?2
Pinacosaurus grangeri ?2
Euoplocephalus tutus ?2
Huayangosaurus taibaii ?2
Hesperosaurus mjosi ??
Stegosaurus stenops 12
Wannanosaurus yansiensis??
*Homalocephale calathocercos*12
Goyocephale lattimorei ??
Stegoceras validum ??
Prenocephale prenes ??
Micropachycephalosaurus hongtuyanensis 12
Laquintasaura venezuelae 0-
Isaberrysaura mollensis ??

We identified several mistakes in the taxon names from the original study by Han et al. ⁹ and have corrected them in both the data matrix and the manuscript. Specifically, ‘*Haya gravis*’ was updated to “*Haya griva*”, and “*Iguanodon atherfieldensis*” was changed to “*Mantellisaurus atherfieldensis*”.

6. Phylogenetic analysis using Fonseca et al. ¹⁰’s data matrix

We also added the scorings of *Archaeocursor asiaticus* into the data matrix of Fonseca *et al.* ¹⁰. According to the protocol outlined by Fonseca et al. ¹⁰, *Pareisactus evrostos* was deactivated, *Euparkeria capensis* was designed as the outgroup, and fifty-five characters were treated as additive (ordered): 12, 63, 99, 160, 177, 197, 202, 203, 238, 258, 261, 331, 375, 410, 414, 427, 439, 446, 452, 462, 481, 500, 502, 503, 506, 513, 528, 536, 537, 539, 558, 560, 586, 588, 608, 612, 621, 622, 642, 678, 686, 688, 708, 724, 742, 744, 752, 762, 785, 795, 833, 838, 849, 866, and 909. Phylogenetic analysis was performed using TNT v.1.1. The tree search employed the ‘New

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